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Article in *Journal of Computational Physics* · June 2020

DOI: 10.1016/j.jcp.2020.109717

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A higher-order accurate surface tension modelling volume-of-fluid scheme for 2D curvilinear meshes

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Abstract

This paper proposes a higher-order accurate curvature calculation method for volume-of-fluid (VOF) based surface tension modelling on 2D curvilinear meshes. The scheme extends the interface reconstruction component of the height function (HF) method to curvilinear meshes in 2D. Linear reconstructions are computed in each column overlapping the interface, which results in a piecewise-linear (PLIC) representation of the free-surface. This is done in a volume conservative manner by employing a novel sweep-line algorithm. The interface curvature is then computed analytically by fitting either second- or fourth-order polynomials to local stencils of PLIC facets. Formal second- and fourth-order accuracy of interface curvature is demonstrated by comparing numerical results with a variety of analytical interface definitions. The curvature algorithm is implemented into a balanced-force continuum-surface-force surface tension scheme for variable-density flows. Second- and fourth-order accuracy are again demonstrated for the Laplace pressure jump in the simulation of a stationary bubble with a high liquid-gas density ratio. **Lastly, second-order accuracy is demonstrated in computing the frequency of an inviscid oscillating droplet in zero gravity.**

Keywords: Surface tension, Higher order, Curvilinear meshes, Curvature, Volume of fluid, Interface reconstruction

1. Introduction

The accurate simulation of unsteady surface-tension-dominant interfacial flows is of increasing importance in the field of computational fluid dynamics (CFD). In such cases, resolving the interface curvature accurately is crucial for avoiding the generation of so-called ‘spurious’ or ‘parasitic’ currents [1–3]. The volume-of-fluid (VOF) method [4] is widely used for surface tension modelling, and is well known for its mass conservation property. However, compared to level-set (LS) methods [5], accurately computing geometric attributes like the interface normal and curvature is challenging, particularly on unstructured meshes [6–8]. This is because VOF methods capture the interface using a discontinuous volume fraction field, while LS methods track the interface using a smooth and differentiable level-set distance function [8].

The majority of the VOF methods require that the interface be reconstructed from the volume fraction field before the evaluation of interface curvature. Pilliod and Puckett [9] introduced the second-order accurate ELVIRA method for interface reconstruction on Cartesian meshes. The Height Function (HF) method [10–14] has been used extensively for the computation of curvature. The HF method constructs ‘columns’ of control volumes that straddle the interface, after which the curvature is computed from a stencil of columns by computing the height of the interface in each column. On 2D Cartesian meshes, the HF method yields second-order accuracy of curvature when three-column stencils are used, and has been shown to yield fourth-order accuracy when five-column stencils are used [13, 15]. Baltussen *et al.* [16] developed the Tensile Force (TF) method, which directly computes the surface tension force exerted on each interface element by summing the tensile forces exerted by neighbouring interface elements. The TF method was shown to be more accurate than the HF method for large interfaces (with Eötvös number, $Eu > 10$). **Recently, Owkes**

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and Desjardins [17] introduced a second-order accurate mesh-decoupled HF method, which was shown to perform better than the standard HF method on coarser meshes. This was achieved by enabling the construction of columns in directions misaligned with the coordinate axes.

Recent developments in surface tension modelling has included adaptive mesh refinement as well as non-orthogonal meshes. The latter includes work on curvilinear meshes [6, 8, 18]. The HF method was used by Popinet [12] for surface tension computations on adaptively refined Cartesian meshes. Francois and Swartz [13] generalised the HF method for non-uniform orthogonal meshes. Ito *et al.* [19] adapted the HF concept directly on 2D unstructured meshes, but achieved less than first-order accuracy for curvature. Ivey and Moin [14] later extended HF to convex polyhedral meshes by conservatively interpolating the VOF field onto a superimposed Cartesian mesh. Renardy and Renardy [20] developed the PROST method, that computes the curvature from a weighted parabolic fit, in a manner that locally minimises the error in the volume fraction field on Cartesian meshes. This is achieved by an iterative procedure, where the volume fractions of each control volume intersected by the curve are approximately evaluated at each iteration, until an objective function is minimised. Evrard *et al.* [21] recently generalised this method for 2D unstructured meshes, and demonstrated second-order accuracy of curvature. Jibben *et al.* [7] developed a 3D method for arbitrary polyhedral meshes where a paraboloid is fitted to piecewise-linear reconstructions (PLIC) of the interface in a locally volume conservative manner. Their method was shown to yield between first- and second-order accuracy of curvature. The current work employs a 2D specialisation of the work of Jibben *et al.*, and extends to higher-order polynomial fits.

The aim of this research is to develop VOF-based surface tension modelling capabilities on curvilinear meshes for vertex-centred finite volume applications. Curvilinear meshes have numerous applications in CFD, and are particularly well suited to curved geometries like satellite fuel tanks. Huang *et al.* [18] used an LS approach to model air/water turbulent flows around ships on overset curvilinear meshes. Wang *et al.* [6] developed a VOF method that reconstructs the LS distance function on a computational domain, onto which a curvilinear physical domain is mapped. More recently, Cao *et al.* [8] developed a coupled LS-VOF method that directly reconstructs the distance function on the physical domain. However, both the aforementioned methods achieved less than first-order accuracy of curvature. This is because, in both cases, the curvature is computed via a second-derivative of a second-order accurate distance function. Additionally, both methods are limited to physical domains that can be mapped onto a rectangular computational domain.

Figure 1: A typical curvilinear mesh used in this work – (a) a curvilinear mesh of a circular domain, and (b) a close-up of the inner structured region showing four knot points.

As compared to the cited work, the method proposed in this paper extends the following aspects to 2D curvilinear meshes for the purpose of surface tension computation – (i) the interface reconstruction component of the HF method [10–12], and (ii) the notion of volume-conservative parabolic fitting in the PROST method [20]. A typical mesh is shown in Fig. 1, with the underlying discretisation method being vertex-centred finite volume. However, the proposed scheme is directly applicable to cell-centred methods as well. Columns of control volumes that straddle the interface are identified, and the interface is reconstructed in a volume conservative manner by employing a novel sweep-line

algorithm based on the convex decomposition [14, 22, 23] of the control volumes in each column. The interface curvature is then computed analytically by locally fitting second- or fourth-order polynomials to the reconstructed interface. This is done in a manner that adheres to the volume conservation property of the interface reconstruction as closely as possible [7].

To the best of the authors' knowledge, no scheme currently exists that employs the same strategy for surface tension modelling on curvilinear meshes as that proposed in this paper. The scheme works generically in regions of the mesh whose connectivity graph is similar to that of a structured mesh. In order to handle cases where the interface passes through any of the four vertices labelled as 'knots' in Fig. 1, the algorithms outlined here need to be specialised. **Since the connectivity at these vertices could prevent the successful construction of columns, a tractable solution would be to interpolate the interface curvature computed at neighbouring interface vertices.** However, this falls beyond the scope of this paper.

The proposed scheme was implemented in the *Elemental*[®] multi-physics code [24–28]. The first step in demonstrating higher-order accuracy of interface curvature is the VOF field initialisation. For this purpose, we employ the arbitrary grid initialiser (AGI) tool in *Elemental*[®], developed by Jones *et al.* [28], to initialise the VOF field to machine-precision accuracy.

Section 2 details the underlying governing equations employed to model surface tension for variable-density flows. The novel curvature computation methodology for curvilinear meshes is detailed in Section 3. Finally, a rigorous analysis of the accuracy and computational efficiency of the overall scheme is carried out in Section 4.

2. Governing Equations

The incompressible Navier-Stokes equations with surface tension for variable-density two-phase flow can be expressed as

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) - \nabla \cdot (\mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T)) + \nabla p = \sigma\kappa\delta_s\mathbf{n} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial\rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{u}) &= 0 \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{u} \equiv \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the velocity field, $p \equiv p(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the pressure field, $\rho \equiv \rho(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the fluid density, and $\mu \equiv \mu(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the dynamic viscosity. In the surface tension source term, σ is the surface tension coefficient, κ is the interface curvature, \mathbf{n} is the interface normal, and δ_s is the Dirac delta function which concentrates the surface tension contribution only on the interface. Note that the acceleration/gravity source term is not accounted for in this work. The interface is tracked by the volume fraction equation

$$\frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha\mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (3)$$

where, given two fluids - Fluid 0 and Fluid 1, α is the volume fraction of Fluid 1. The density and viscosity in Eqs. (1) and (2) are computed as

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(\alpha) &= \alpha\rho_1 + (1 - \alpha)\rho_0 \\ \mu(\alpha) &= \alpha\mu_1 + (1 - \alpha)\mu_0 \end{aligned}$$

where the 0 and 1 subscripts denote the attributes of the respective fluids. The surface tension source term in Eq. (1) is approximated using the continuum-surface-force (CSF) method of Brackbill *et al.* [29] as

$$\sigma\kappa\delta_s\mathbf{n} \approx \sigma\kappa\nabla\alpha$$

where, $\nabla\alpha$ is the gradient of the volume fraction field. **The temporal and balanced-force spatial discretisation of the governing equations is outlined in Appendices A and B, respectively.** A novel methodology for the computation of the interface curvature κ is detailed next.

3. Curvature Computation Methodology for Curvilinear Meshes

Similar to the HF method, the proposed scheme first identifies columns of control volumes that straddle the interface. However, instead of interpreting the position of the interface as a height in each column, the current method computes a linear reconstruction (henceforth referred to as a ‘PLIC facet’) of the portion of the interface overlapping each column.

Figure 2: Procedure for computing curvature from a stencil of PLIC facets reconstructing an underlying VOF interface. (a) Three adjacent columns. (b) The vertex-centred median dual-cells of the mesh vertices in each column. (c) Conservative reconstruction of PLIC facets (red line segments) corresponding to the interface normals (blue arrows). (d) Polynomial curve fit (blue curve) through a stencil of three PLIC facets.

Three adjacent columns are illustrated in Fig. 2(a) whose corresponding columns of control volumes are shown in Fig. 2(b), with the PLIC facets constructed in these columns shown in Fig. 2(c). Each PLIC facet is constructed such that the volume of a reference fluid in the column is conserved. A polynomial (2^{nd} or 4^{th} order) is then fitted to local stencils of PLIC facets (*i.e.* a combination of three or five PLIC facets) in a manner that minimises the signed area bounded by the facets and the curve [7], as illustrated in Fig. 2(d). This is detailed in Section 3.4. The curvature is then computed analytically from the polynomial fit.

As is the case with HF on Cartesian meshes, it is challenging to compute the curvature in regions of the interface where the directions of the columns switch. On curvilinear meshes, this challenge is exacerbated by the fact that the mesh spacing in one mesh direction may vary significantly from that of the other – this is the case in anisotropic regions of the mesh. This results in the interface being represented more accurately by PLIC facets constructed in columns oriented in the direction with smaller column widths. This **discrepancy** in the accuracy of the PLIC facets becomes a concern for curvature computations where the directions of the columns switch for two reasons.

Firstly, it was found that stencils with a combination of PLIC facets of different accuracies (due to switching of column directions) hugely compromises the accuracy of the associated polynomial curve fit. Secondly, in almost all cases, such stencils were found to consist of overlapping PLIC facets, which further compromises the accuracy of the polynomial fit. These issues are addressed by ensuring that curvature stencils only consist of PLIC facets constructed in columns that are aligned in the same general direction, *i.e.* within 45° of each other. Additionally, by creating a region of overlap where the column directions switch, as that demarcated by the white dashed line in Fig. 3, the curvature can be computed by interpolating the nodal curvature computed from overlapping stencils (detailed in Section 3.6). The following sections describe the involved curvature computation procedure in detail.

3.1. Column Construction

The first step in the proposed scheme is to identify suitable columns of control volumes that overlap the interface. In a given volume fraction field α , either one or two columns are constructed at each interface vertex (a vertex i is an interface vertex if $\alpha_i < 0.5$ and it is connected to a vertex j with $\alpha_j \geq 0.5$). The direction in which the columns are constructed depends on the normal at each interface vertex, which is refined iteratively (detailed in Section 3.5).

Figure 3: Portion of a circular VOF interface showing columns constructed in two directions, with a region of overlap. The white dashed line demarcates the region of overlapping columns (which results in overlapping PLIC facets constructed in these columns).

The use of the HF method to compute the interface position has to date relied, either directly [11, 13] or indirectly [12, 14], on structured Cartesian meshes, where each column is aligned with one of the primary coordinate axes. However, in the case of curvilinear meshes, columns may lie along arbitrary directions. This requires having to compute angles between each interface normal and the two edges between which it is bounded (illustrated in Fig. 4 as edges \overline{ij} and \overline{ik}). The angle θ between the two edges and the interface normal determines which of the two edges along which a column is to be constructed. Additionally, in order to ensure a region of overlapping columns where required (as seen in Fig. 3), the angle between the bounding edges is divided into three sectors, labelled as A, B, and C in Fig. 4. The sector within which the interface normal lies determines whether or not the associated interface vertex lies in an overlapping region.

Figure 4: Sector divisions between the two edges bounding an interface normal for determining the number of columns to be constructed at an interface vertex. The blue curve represents the interface. (a) Angles associated with each sector, (b) the normal lies in sector A resulting in a single column, (c) the normal lies in sector B resulting in two columns, (d) the normal lies in sector C resulting in a single column.

With reference to Fig. 4, an interface vertex lies in an overlapping region if its interface normal lies in sector B. Two columns are constructed at all vertices in an overlapping region, and only one otherwise – the red arrows in the figure signify the directions in which columns are constructed. Fig. 4(a) illustrates that the angles of the sectors are defined by an angle $\phi = \frac{1}{2}(\theta + \theta_B)$, where $\theta_B \in [0, \frac{\pi}{4}]$ is a user-defined angle prescribed for sector B in the figure. In this paper, we prescribe $\theta_B = \frac{\pi}{6}$. Algorithm 1 outlines the pseudo-code for the above procedure.

Algorithm 1 Column construction at an interface vertex for a given set of directions.

Input: Interface vertex i , interface normal \mathbf{n}_i , column overlap angle θ_B , volume fraction tolerance α_{tol}

Output: The array of columns, Z , that are to be constructed at interface vertex i .

```

1: procedure CONSTRUCTCOLUMNS( $i, \mathbf{n}_i, \theta_B, \alpha_{tol}$ )
2:   set  $E \leftarrow$  the set of two edges connected to vertex  $i$  between which  $\mathbf{n}_i$  is bounded.  $E[0]$  is the edge CCW from
    $\mathbf{n}_i$ , and  $E[1]$  is CW from  $\mathbf{n}_i$ .
3:   set  $\theta \leftarrow$  the angle between the two edges in  $E$ .
4:   set  $\theta_0 \leftarrow$  the angle between the edge  $E[0]$  and  $\mathbf{n}_i$ .
5:   set  $\phi \leftarrow \frac{1}{2}(\theta + \theta_B)$ .
6:
7:    $D = []$  // The array of edge directions in which columns are to be constructed.
8:   if  $\theta_0 < \phi$  then
9:     add  $D \leftarrow$  outward-pointing direction vector (w.r.t.  $i$ ) of edge  $E[0]$ .
10:  end
11:  if  $(\theta - \theta_0) < \phi$  then
12:    add  $D \leftarrow$  outward-pointing direction vector (w.r.t.  $i$ ) of edge  $E[1]$ .
13:  end
14:
15:   $Z = []$  // The array of columns that are to be constructed at vertex  $i$ .
16:  for all  $d \in D$  do
17:     $\zeta = []$  // A column, defined by an array of vertices that it contains.
18:    set  $j \leftarrow i$ 
19:    while  $\alpha_j < (1 - \alpha_{tol})$  do // Traverse the mesh into Fluid 1, starting from vertex  $i$ 
20:      set  $j \leftarrow$  the vertex connected to  $j$  whose outward-pointing direction vector (w.r.t.  $j$ ) is nearest to  $d$ .
21:    end
22:    while  $\alpha_j > \alpha_{tol}$  do // Traverse the mesh into Fluid 0, starting from vertex  $j$ 
23:      add  $\zeta \leftarrow j$ 
24:      set  $j \leftarrow$  the vertex connected to  $j$  whose outward-pointing direction vector (w.r.t.  $j$ ) is nearest to  $-d$ .
25:    end
26:    add  $Z \leftarrow \zeta$ 
27:  end
28:  return  $Z$ 

```

3.2. Conservative Interface Reconstruction

A PLIC facet is constructed in each column, ζ . This is done in a conservative manner by associating to ζ , the total volume of a reference fluid (Fluid 1 for the remainder of the paper). The interface normal required to construct the PLIC facet is initially seeded by the gradient of the volume fraction field $\nabla \alpha_i$, at the interface vertex associated to ζ . This normal is then refined iteratively, as detailed in Section 3.5, in order to achieve higher-order accuracy of the curvature computation. The total reference fluid volume in ζ that must be conserved when constructing its PLIC facet is computed as

$$\mathcal{V}_{ref} = \sum_{i \in \zeta} \alpha_i \mathcal{V}_i \quad (4)$$

where α_i and \mathcal{V}_i respectively, are the volume fraction and volume of the median dual-cell at a mesh vertex $i \in \zeta$. Considering the current scheme is specialised to 2D, note that the notions of ‘area’ and ‘volume’ are used analogously

in this section.

The development of robust and efficient tools, for constructing the unique PLIC facet that matches \mathcal{V}_{ref} and is orthogonal to a prescribed normal, has received much attention from the PLIC-VOF community in recent years [14, 22, 23, 30–34]. The existing literature for interface reconstruction can be broadly categorised into three approaches based on the geometry of the polygon within which the PLIC facet is constructed. These are – (i) convex polygons [31–33], (ii) arbitrary polygons with convex decomposition (CD) (*i.e.* the splitting of a non-convex polygon into triangles) [14, 22, 23], and (iii) arbitrary polygons without CD [34]. The common factor in all these approaches is the use of a sweep-line approach to ‘sweep’ through the polygon/s until the line that exactly cuts off the reference volume is determined. This requires the sorting of all polygonal vertices in the direction of the prescribed normal.

A CD approach is employed in the current work, where the median dual-cells of the mesh vertices in ζ are decomposed into triangles. This is achieved by connecting the mesh vertices with the centroids of the surrounding edges and cells. This results in the triangulation, T_ζ . An example of a column and its corresponding triangulation is depicted in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b). In order to sort the vertices of T_ζ , a signed distance $\eta(\mathbf{x})$ is assigned to each vertex $\mathbf{x} \in T_\zeta$, and is defined as

$$\eta_{\mathbf{x}} = \eta(\mathbf{x}) = (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{ref,\zeta}) \cdot \mathbf{n}_p \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{n}_p = -\mathbf{n}_i$ is the PLIC facet normal, and \mathbf{n}_i is the interface normal associated to ζ . Further, $\mathbf{x}_{ref,\zeta}$ is some fixed reference vertex in T_ζ . Figs. 5(c) and 5(d) depict the sorting of the vertices of T_ζ and the corresponding iso- η lines passing through each vertex. In this paper, $\mathcal{V}(\eta)$ denotes the volume of the intersection between T_ζ and the region below the iso- η line, and is defined as

$$\mathcal{V}(\eta) = \int_{\Omega_\eta} d\mathcal{V} \quad \text{where} \quad \Omega_\eta = T_\zeta \cap \{ \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid \eta(\mathbf{x}) \leq \eta \} \quad (6)$$

The interface reconstruction problem can now be **concisely** restated as – computing η_p such that $\mathcal{V}(\eta_p) = \mathcal{V}_{ref}$, where η_p is the η -value of the PLIC facet.

Figure 5: Interface reconstruction procedure – (a) A three-vertex column ζ , (b) decomposition of ζ into its associated triangulation T_ζ , (c) sorting of the vertices of T_ζ by the signed distance function $\eta(\mathbf{x})$, and (d) a close-up of a triangle in T_ζ . The blue curve represents the interface, the blue arrow the interface normal evaluated at the interface vertex, and the red line the PLIC facet which conserves the reference fluid volume \mathcal{V}_{ref} in ζ .

The proposed method consists of the so-called ‘bracketing’ procedure to find η_{lo} and η_{up} (see Fig. 5(c)), followed by a novel method of solving η_p from the analytical definition of $\mathcal{V}(\eta)$ when restricted to $\eta \in [\eta_{lo}, \eta_{up}]$. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, existing methods based on CD compute η_p by the use of iterative approaches like the secant and bisection methods used by Ahn and Shashkov [22], Brent’s method by Ivey and Moin [14], and the Muller-Newton

method by Skarysz *et al.* [23].

Similar to the present work, López *et al.* [34] recently proposed a scheme that combines bracketing with an analytical solution procedure, but with no requirement for CD. The scheme of López *et al.* is proposed to be a lot less costly than CD approaches. However, Section 4.5 details why this would not be the case, specifically in the context of the present work. Additionally, CD significantly simplifies the bracketing procedure, as will be seen shortly.

It must be noted that although the focus of the present work is to construct a PLIC facet in a column ζ , the procedures outlined in this section are directly applicable for interface reconstruction in arbitrary polygons too. The following sections describe the bracketing procedure and the novel analytical solution procedure for computing η_p in T_ζ , or any triangulation of an arbitrary polygon.

3.2.1. Bracketing the Solution

For a general column in 2D, $\mathcal{V}(\eta)$ (see Eq. (6)) is monotonically increasing with η , and is piecewise-quadratic with C^0 continuity at all η_x iso-lines passing through vertices $\mathbf{x} \in T_\zeta$. Bracketing the solution involves finding

$$\eta_{lo} = \max\{\eta_x, \forall \mathbf{x} \in T_\zeta \mid \mathcal{V}(\eta_x) \leq \mathcal{V}_{ref}\} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\eta_{up} = \min\{\eta_x, \forall \mathbf{x} \in T_\zeta \mid \eta_x > \eta_{lo}\}$$

and computing $\mathcal{V}(\eta_{lo})$, as depicted by the light blue region in Fig. 5(c). As mentioned previously, this allows for the domain of $\mathcal{V}(\eta)$ to be restricted to $\eta \in [\eta_{lo}, \eta_{up}]$, where the behaviour of $\mathcal{V}(\eta)$ is defined by a single quadratic equation. Solving Eq. (7) requires explicitly computing the cut-off volume $\mathcal{V}(\eta_x)$ iteratively at vertices $\mathbf{x} \in T_\zeta$ starting with an initial guess, until the required condition for η_{lo} is satisfied. As an initial guess, the η_x that is nearest to the η -value of a vertex interpolated to $\alpha = 0.5$ is used. For an edge $e_{ij} \in \zeta$ where $0.5 \in [\alpha_i, \alpha_j]$, this vertex is computed via linear interpolation of the vertices \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j . With this initial guess, Eq. (7) is solved in at most 3 iterations for all tests performed in Section 4.

Considering Eq. (6), computing $\mathcal{V}(\eta_x)$ in each iteration involves computing the net volume intersected by the region below the η_x iso-line and each triangle in T_ζ . Whether a triangle is below, above, or intersected by the η_x iso-line is determined by how many of its vertices have η -values greater than η_x . If all vertices have $\eta \leq \eta_x$, the triangle is below the η_x iso-line, and contributes a volume equal to its area (for improved computational efficiency, the volume contributions of such triangles are stored for reuse, should they remain un-intersected in subsequent iterations). If all vertices have $\eta > \eta_x$, the triangle is above the η_x iso-line, and contributes zero volume. Either of the two remaining cases (either 1 or 2 vertices have $\eta \leq \eta_x$) indicate that the triangle is intersected by the η_x iso-line, in which case the two intersection points are computed using the function

$$\mathbf{x}_\cap(\eta, \mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) = r_\cap \mathbf{x}_j + (1 - r_\cap) \mathbf{x}_i, \quad \text{with } r_\cap = \frac{\eta - \eta(\mathbf{x}_i)}{\eta(\mathbf{x}_j) - \eta(\mathbf{x}_i)} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j are two vertices such that $\eta \in [\min\{\eta(\mathbf{x}_i), \eta(\mathbf{x}_j)\}, \max\{\eta(\mathbf{x}_i), \eta(\mathbf{x}_j)\}]$. Computing the volume contribution of an intersected triangle is straightforward, since it always splits into two sub-polygons – a sub-triangle and a sub-quadrilateral. Therefore, the volume contribution is the area of the sub-polygon whose vertices all have $\eta \leq \eta_x$. When required, the area of the sub-quadrilateral can be computed by subtracting the area of the sub-triangle from that of the parent triangle. In all other cases, only the area of the sub-triangle need be computed. Once η_{lo} is computed, η_{up} is then simply the η -value of the nearest vertex above η_{lo} in the sorted vertex list.

It should now be clear that the convex decomposition of ζ makes the bracketing procedure a lot more straightforward than it would be if ζ were not triangulated. The novel analytical solution procedure in the bracketed region is detailed next.

3.2.2. Analytical Equation in Bracketed Region

In this section, we outline the formulation of the quadratic equation that describes the behaviour of $\mathcal{V}(\eta)$ when restricted to $\eta \in [\eta_{lo}, \eta_{up}]$. This equation is then used to compute η_p , the η -value of the PLIC facet (red line in Fig. 5) that (i) conserves the reference fluid volume \mathcal{V}_{ref} and (ii) is orthogonal to the pre-computed interface normal. Property (i) is enforced by accounting for the additional volume $\Delta\mathcal{V}_p = \mathcal{V}_{ref} - \mathcal{V}(\eta_{lo})$, depicted as the light red region in Fig.

5(c), and (ii) is already enforced by virtue of the orientation of the sweep-line. To compute the η -value increment $\Delta\eta_p$, that is associated to $\Delta\mathcal{V}_p$, an incremental volume function $\Delta\mathcal{V}(\Delta\eta)$ is introduced.

As seen in Figs. 5(c) and 5(d), determining $\Delta\mathcal{V}(\Delta\eta)$ involves accounting for the individual volume increments $\Delta\mathcal{V}_\tau(\Delta\eta)$ in each triangle τ , that is intersected by the η_{lo} iso-line. For the remainder of this section, $T_{\zeta,lo} \subset T_\zeta$ shall denote this sub-triangulation. For illustrative purposes, the example triangle shown in Fig. 5(d) shall be used to represent the general case of a triangle $\tau \in T_{\zeta,lo}$. Fig. 6 demonstrates that $\Delta\mathcal{V}_\tau(\Delta\eta)$ must be computed for two distinct sections in τ , which shall be referred to as ‘sweep-sections’.

Figure 6: Volume increment function for a triangle τ – (a) sweep-sections of τ , (b) the incremental volume in sweep-section s_0 , and (c) the incremental volume in sweep-section s_1

Each sweep-section has a unique quadratic equation defining $\Delta\mathcal{V}_\tau(\Delta\eta)$, whose coefficients are determined by the pair of edges that bound the sweep-section. To this end, we first define an arbitrary normalised (with respect to the PLIC facet normal \mathbf{n}_p) tangent vector $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{mn}$ of an edge that joins vertices \mathbf{x}_m and \mathbf{x}_n as

$$\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{mn} = \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbf{t}_{mn}}{\mathbf{t}_{mn} \cdot \mathbf{n}_p} & \text{if } \mathbf{t}_{mn} \cdot \mathbf{n}_p \neq 0 \\ \mathbf{0} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}, \text{ where } \mathbf{t}_{mn} = \mathbf{x}_n - \mathbf{x}_m \text{ and } \eta(\mathbf{x}_n) \geq \eta(\mathbf{x}_m). \quad (9)$$

Here, $m, n \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ are local vertex indices of τ , as per Fig. 6. The second condition in Eq. (9) accounts for degenerate cases, which occur when a sweep-section collapses as a result of one of its bounding edges being parallel to the sweep-line. Such sweep-sections have zero volume contribution.

The reader is now reminded that since $\eta(\mathbf{x})$ is the signed distance between the iso- η lines passing through \mathbf{x} and $\mathbf{x}_{ref,\zeta}$ (see Eq. (5)), the difference between two η -values is the signed distance between their associated iso- η lines. With this in mind, the heights h and h_{lo} shown in Figs. 6(b) and 6(c) are computed from

$$h(\eta, \mathbf{x}_{ref,\tau}) = \eta - \eta(\mathbf{x}_{ref,\tau}) \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_{ref,\tau}$ is a reference vertex in τ , which is defined as

$$\mathbf{x}_{ref,\tau} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{x}_0, & \text{for sweep-section } s_0 \text{ (see Fig. 6(a))} \\ \mathbf{x}_2, & \text{for sweep-section } s_1 \text{ (see Fig. 6(a))} \end{cases}$$

Using the η_{lo} iso-line as the datum, the sweep-line increment $\Delta\eta$ is defined as

$$\Delta\eta = \eta - \eta_{lo} = h - h_{lo}, \quad \Delta\eta \in [0, (\eta_{up} - \eta_{lo})] \quad (11)$$

Combining Eqs. (9) - (11), and referring to Fig. 6, $\Delta\mathcal{V}_\tau(\Delta\eta)$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta\mathcal{V}_\tau(\Delta\eta) &= k \left[\frac{1}{2} |(h\hat{\mathbf{t}}_a) \times (h\hat{\mathbf{t}}_b)| - \frac{1}{2} |(h_{lo}\hat{\mathbf{t}}_a) \times (h_{lo}\hat{\mathbf{t}}_b)| \right] \\
&= \frac{k}{2} (h^2 - h_{lo}^2) |\hat{\mathbf{t}}_a \times \hat{\mathbf{t}}_b| \\
&= \frac{k}{2} ((h_{lo} + \Delta\eta)^2 - h_{lo}^2) |\hat{\mathbf{t}}_a \times \hat{\mathbf{t}}_b| \\
&= \frac{k}{2} (\Delta\eta^2 + 2h_{lo}\Delta\eta) |\hat{\mathbf{t}}_a \times \hat{\mathbf{t}}_b|
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where the normalised tangents, $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_a$ and $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_b$, of the bounding edges of the sweep-sections are defined using Eq. (9) as,

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\mathbf{t}}_a &= \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{02} \\
\hat{\mathbf{t}}_b &= \begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{01}, & \text{for sweep-section } s_0 \\ \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{12}, & \text{for sweep-section } s_1 \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

and k ensures that $\Delta\mathcal{V}_\tau(\Delta\eta) \geq 0$ for sweep-section s_1 (Fig. 6(c)), and is defined as

$$k = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for sweep-section } s_0 \\ -1, & \text{for sweep-section } s_1 \end{cases}$$

Eq. (12) can be restated as

$$\Delta\mathcal{V}_\tau(\Delta\eta) = c_{2,\tau}\Delta\eta^2 + c_{1,\tau}\Delta\eta \tag{13}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
c_{1,\tau} &= kh_{lo} |\hat{\mathbf{t}}_a \times \hat{\mathbf{t}}_b| \\
c_{2,\tau} &= \frac{k}{2} |\hat{\mathbf{t}}_a \times \hat{\mathbf{t}}_b|
\end{aligned}$$

are the quadratic coefficients that are to be computed for each triangle $\tau \in T_{\zeta,lo}$. Using Eq. (13), $\Delta\mathcal{V}(\Delta\eta)$ can now be expressed as the sum

$$\Delta\mathcal{V}(\Delta\eta) = \sum_{\tau \in T_{\zeta,lo}} \Delta\mathcal{V}_\tau(\Delta\eta) = C_2\Delta\eta^2 + C_1\Delta\eta$$

where

$$C_j = \sum_{\tau \in T_{\zeta,lo}} c_{j,\tau}, \text{ for } j \in \{1, 2\}$$

Having obtained the function $\Delta\mathcal{V}(\Delta\eta)$ that describes the incremental volume in $[\eta_{lo}, \eta_{up}]$, what is left to be computed is $\Delta\eta_p \in [0, (\eta_{up} - \eta_{lo})]$ such that $\Delta\mathcal{V}(\Delta\eta_p) = \Delta\mathcal{V}_p$. This procedure is outlined next.

3.2.3. PLIC Facet Computation Procedure

The volume increment equation $\Delta\mathcal{V}(\Delta\eta)$, developed in the previous section, is now used to compute the PLIC facet for a column ζ . Given the coefficients C_j from Eq. (14), and the known volume increment $\Delta\mathcal{V}_p = \mathcal{V}_{ref} - \mathcal{V}(\eta_{lo})$, the corresponding sweep-line increment from the η_{lo} iso-line (see Fig. 7), can be computed by solving for the root, $\Delta\eta_p \in [0, (\eta_{up} - \eta_{lo})]$, of the function

$$f(\Delta\eta, \Delta\mathcal{V}_p) = \Delta\mathcal{V}(\Delta\eta) - \Delta\mathcal{V}_p = C_2\Delta\eta^2 + C_1\Delta\eta - \Delta\mathcal{V}_p$$

Note that the above has exactly one root in the $[0, (\eta_{up} - \eta_{lo})]$ range, as $\Delta\mathcal{V}(\Delta\eta)$ is monotonically increasing. The η -value associated to the PLIC facet position can now be computed as $\eta_p = \eta_{lo} + \Delta\eta_p$.

Figure 7: Close-up of Fig. 5(c) showing the reference fluid volume increment ΔV_p (and corresponding sweep-line increment $\Delta \eta_p$) to be added from the η_{lo} iso- η line up to the PLIC facet.

The two endpoints of the PLIC facet are defined by the intersection of the η_p iso-line and exactly two edges on the boundary of T_{ζ} . Once these bounding edges are identified, the endpoints of the PLIC facet can be computed using Eq. (8).

The procedure outlined thus far is fully volume conservative. As mentioned previously, the accuracy of the orientation of the PLIC facet is limited by that with which the local interface normal can be computed from the available information. Since the normals computed from the volume fraction field do not result in sufficient accuracy (demonstrated in Section 4.2), this is to be improved, and is discussed in Section 3.5. The following section details how stencils of columns are assembled for the computation of interface normals and curvature.

3.3. Column Stencil Construction

Following the steps detailed thus far allows for the interface to be represented by a set of PLIC facets. Since each PLIC facet is a linear reconstruction, a collection of PLIC facets (which is referred to as a ‘stencil’) can be utilised to compute the interface normals and curvature. Both these attributes are computed in a column-wise manner. For reasons that will be made clear shortly, the computed interface normal, curvature, and PLIC facet data are uniquely associated with each column for later retrieval. Therefore, by identifying stencils of columns, the corresponding stencil of PLIC facets can be inferred from the column data-structure.

Figure 8: The two types of stencils for a column ζ_m with neighbouring columns ζ_n , and interface vertex i_m – (a) a symmetric stencil, (b) an asymmetric stencil.

There are two types of column stencils that may arise – these will be referred to as ‘symmetric’ and ‘asymmetric’ stencils, respectively. As mentioned earlier, due to accuracy implications, all stencils consist of PLIC facets con-

structured in columns that are aligned in the same general direction (within 45° of each other). A symmetric stencil is constructed when, for a given column ζ_m , two adjacent columns (or four for fourth-order) that lie within 45° of ζ_m can be found. This results in either a three- or five-column stencil (see Fig. 8(a)) from which an attribute (interface normal or curvature) can be directly computed for the central column ζ_m (detailed in Sections 3.4 - 3.6).

An asymmetric stencil occurs when ζ_m is only neighbored by at most one other column that lies within 45° of it. This typically occurs on both ends of a region where columns overlap (see Fig. 8(b) which is a close-up of Fig. 3). In such cases, a three- or five-column stencil consisting of columns ζ_n in the alternate mesh direction is first identified. Then, the attributes for ζ_m are computed via a polynomial fit through the PLIC facets associated to ζ_n (detailed in Sections 3.5 and 3.6). Algorithm 2 details the column identification procedure for a three-column stencil. Note that a five-column stencil can be constructed by recursively executing Algorithm 2 at the columns on both ends of a three-column stencil.

Algorithm 2 Three-column stencil computation centred around a given column.

Input: Central column ζ_m .

Output: Stencil of three columns Z_m centred around ζ_m , and an index indicating the stencil type.

```

1: procedure COMPUTECOLUMNSTENCIL( $\zeta_m$ )
2:   set  $i_m \leftarrow$  the index of the mesh vertex at which  $\zeta_m$  was constructed.
3:   set  $\mathbf{d}_m \leftarrow$  the unit direction vector of  $\zeta_m$  (red arrows in Fig. 4).
4:   set  $Z \leftarrow$  the array of all columns connected to any vertex that shares a mesh element with vertex  $i$ .
5:    $Z_0 = []$  // The array of columns in  $Z$  whose direction vectors are within  $45^\circ$  of  $\mathbf{d}_m$ .
6:    $Z_1 = []$  // The array of columns in  $Z$  whose direction vectors are not within  $45^\circ$  of  $\mathbf{d}_m$ .
7:   for all  $\zeta_n \in Z$  do // Distinguish between columns that are in-line with  $\zeta_m$  and those that are not.
8:     if  $\zeta_n \neq \zeta_m$  then
9:       set  $\mathbf{d}_n \leftarrow$  the unit direction vector of  $\zeta_n$  (red arrows in Fig. 4).
10:      if  $\mathbf{d}_n \cdot \mathbf{d}_m > \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$  then
11:        add  $Z_0 \leftarrow \zeta_n$  // Aligned.
12:      else
13:        add  $Z_1 \leftarrow \zeta_n$  // Not aligned.
14:      end
15:    end
16:  end
17:
18:   $stenType$  // The stencil type. 0 – Symmetric stencil, 1 – Asymmetric stencil.
19:   $Z_m = []$  // The stencil of columns surrounding  $\zeta_m$ , where  $\zeta_m$  is always the first column.
20:  add  $Z_m \leftarrow \zeta_m$ 
21:  if  $size(Z_0) \geq 2$  then // At least 2 neighbouring columns in-line with  $\zeta_m$ .
22:    add  $Z_m \leftarrow \zeta, \forall \zeta \in Z_0$ 
23:    assert  $size(Z_m) = 3$ 
24:     $stenType = 0$ 
25:  else // Not within  $45^\circ$ .
26:    add  $Z_m \leftarrow \zeta, \forall \zeta \in Z_1$ 
27:    assert  $size(Z_m) = 4$ 
28:     $stenType = 1$ 
29:  end
30:  return  $Z_m, stenType$ 

```

3.4. Polynomial Fitting Through PLIC Facets

This section details the procedure for fitting an n^{th} -order polynomial curve to a stencil of $(n+1)$ PLIC facets. This is for the dual purpose of (i) computing the interface curvature for symmetric stencils, and (ii) the PLIC facet normal for asymmetric stencils. The respective attribute is computed for the column ζ_m in Figs. 8(a) and 8(b). As mentioned

in the previous section, in the case of asymmetric stencils, a polynomial is **fitted** through the PLIC facets constructed in the $(n+1)$ columns aligned in the same general direction (labelled as ζ_n in 8(b)).

The origin of the local coordinate system of the polynomial (shown as the $\xi\eta$ -axis system in Fig. 9) is located at the centroid of the central PLIC facet in the stencil, and the η -axis is aligned with the normal of this facet. The polynomial is **fitted** in a manner that minimises the signed area bounded between the polynomial itself and the $(n+1)$ PLIC facets with respect to the η direction. An example of a parabola **fitted** through three PLIC facets is depicted in Fig. 9(b). This work specialises to 2D, the 3D paraboloid fitting technique introduced by Jibben *et al.* [7], and extends the technique to higher-order polynomial curves. We digress to point out that this method does not result in a polynomial fit that is strictly volume conservative as per the PLIC facet construction procedure. This is because, in the ξ direction, the computed area is bounded at the endpoints of each PLIC facet by lines that are parallel to the η -axis. Therefore, the variation in the width of each column in the η direction is unaccounted for. End of digression.

Figure 9: (a) Parabolic curve **fitted** through three PLIC facets. (b) Volume conserving property of the parabolic fit – the sum of the areas shaded in light blue equals that of the areas shaded in light red.

Once the polynomial has been **fitted**, the required attribute can be computed analytically. Given the following equation for an n^{th} -order polynomial whose coefficients $\mathbf{c} = [c_1 \ c_2 \ \dots \ c_{n+1}]^T$ are to be computed,

$$P_n(\xi) = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} c_i \xi^{i-1}$$

and a linear equation $l_p(\xi)$ representing each PLIC facet p in the stencil, the signed area between the PLIC facets and the polynomial can be minimised by the following functional,

$$E(\mathbf{c}) = \sum_{p=1}^{n+1} \left(\int_{\Omega_p} (P_n(\xi) - l_p(\xi)) d\xi \right)^2 \quad (14)$$

where Ω_p is the domain of PLIC facet p in the local reference frame, and $l_p(\xi)$ is given by,

$$l_p(\xi) = b_{p1} + b_{p2}\xi$$

where $\xi \in [\xi_{\min,p}, \xi_{\max,p}]$ and $\xi_{\min,p}$ and $\xi_{\max,p}$ respectively, are the minimum and maximum ξ -bounds of p in the local coordinate system. The linear coefficients b_{p1} and b_{p2} are computed as,

$$b_{p1} = \frac{\mathbf{n}_p \cdot \mathbf{x}_p}{n_{p,\eta}} \quad \text{and} \quad b_{p2} = -\frac{n_{p,\xi}}{n_{p,\eta}}$$

where $\mathbf{x}_p = (x_{p,\xi}, x_{p,\eta})$ and $\mathbf{n}_p = (n_{p,\xi}, n_{p,\eta})$ are the centroid and normal of PLIC facet p , whose components are expressed in the local coordinate system. Note that this procedure assumes that the normals of all PLIC facets in the stencil are oriented such that $n_{p,\eta} > 0$. Minimising Eq. (14) with respect to the polynomial coefficients \mathbf{c} results in

$$\sum_{p=1}^{n+1} \left(\int_{\Omega_p} (P_n(\xi) - l_p(\xi)) d\xi \right) \left(\int_{\Omega_p} \phi d\xi \right) = 0$$

which needs to be solved for each $\phi \in \{1, \xi, \dots, \xi^n\}$. The integrals $\int_{\Omega_p} \phi d\xi$ are analytically evaluated as

$$s_{pi} = \int_{\Omega_p} \xi^{i-1} d\xi = i^{-1} (\xi_{max,p}^i - \xi_{min,p}^i) \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2, \dots, (n+1)\}$$

This leads to an $(n+1) \times (n+1)$ linear system for the coefficients \mathbf{c} , which is solved via Gauss elimination with back substitution,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A}\mathbf{c} &= \mathbf{d} \\ \text{where,} \\ A_{ij} &= \sum_{p=1}^{n+1} s_{pi}s_{pj}, \quad d_i = \sum_{p=1}^{n+1} \left(s_{pi} \sum_{k=1}^2 s_{pk}b_{pk} \right) \end{aligned}$$

The equations and algorithms outlined thus far enable the computation of normals and curvature from the polynomial fit. The following section outlines the interface normal computation procedure for both stencil types.

3.5. Refinement of Interface Normals

It was found that the use of the gradient of the volume fraction field for the construction of PLIC facets causes a staggering in the orientations of facets over the interface, as seen in Fig. 12(a). This naturally impairs the accuracy and smoothness of the computed interface curvature. This is addressed by adopting an iterative interface normal refinement procedure, which utilises stencils of PLIC facets constructed in the previous iteration. This iterative procedure hugely improves the accuracy of the interface normals and thereby that of the interface curvature (see results in Section 4.2).

As a change in the interface normals results in a change in the orientation and position of the PLIC facets, this approach inevitably requires that the PLIC facets be reconstructed at each iteration using the procedure that was outlined in Section 3.2. Further, the columns themselves need to be reconstructed at the beginning of each iteration, as the interface normals change between iterations. This iterative procedure makes the proposed method significantly more expensive than the HF method, and optimisations to the overall algorithm will be investigated in future work. However, it is worth noting that the number of iterations required to converge the interface normals decreases for finer mesh resolutions. This is a result of the improvement in accuracy of the volume fraction gradients utilised in the first iteration. Sections 3.5.1 and 3.5.2 detail the normal computation procedure for the two column stencil types.

3.5.1. Symmetric Stencil

Fig. 10 is an example of a PLIC facet stencil derived from a symmetric stencil of columns, as that shown in Fig. 8(a) – the columns have been omitted for clarity.

Figure 10: The interface normal computation procedure for a symmetric stencil.

All the PLIC facets in the stencil have been constructed in the k^{th} iteration of the iterative procedure that is outlined shortly, in Section 3.5.3. The normal \mathbf{n}_m^{k+1} for PLIC facet p_m is computed via an inverse-distance weighting as

$$\mathbf{n}_m^{k+1} = \mathcal{N} \left(\sum_{n=1}^2 \frac{\mathbf{n}_{mn}^k}{|\mathbf{x}_n^k - \mathbf{x}_m^k|} \right) \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{n}_{mn}^k denotes the normal to the dashed line created by connecting the respective PLIC centroids (see Fig. 10), and $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{v})$ normalises a vector \mathbf{v} .

3.5.2. Asymmetric Stencil

Fig. 11 illustrates the procedure for computing the interface normal for an asymmetric stencil. The three PLIC facets demarcated by the green dashed line in Fig. 11(a) are all constructed in columns that are aligned in the same general direction. Therefore, a parabola can be fitted through these PLIC facets, and the normal \mathbf{n}_m^{k+1} of PLIC facet p_m can be analytically computed from the parabola in the manner detailed shortly. The origin of the local axis system of the parabola is located at the centroid \mathbf{x}_2^k of PLIC facet p_2 , and the η -axis is aligned with the normal \mathbf{n}_2^{k+1} (see Fig. 11(b)), which results in faster convergence compared to when \mathbf{n}_2^k is used. This requires that the normal for p_2 be computed prior to the computation of \mathbf{n}_m^{k+1} . In each iteration, this is achieved by computing the normals for all symmetric stencils before doing so for the asymmetric ones. After the parabola has been constructed, \mathbf{n}_m^{k+1} is computed as the analytical normal of the point on the parabola that is nearest to the centroid \mathbf{x}_m^k of p_m (see Fig. 11(c)).

Figure 11: The interface normal computation procedure for an asymmetric stencil – (a) demarcation of the PLIC facets in the asymmetric stencil, (b) the position of the local coordinate system at p_2 , and (c) the normal of p_m , inferred from the normal of the parabola passing through p_1 to p_3 .

Given the parabola $P_2(\xi) = c_1 + c_2\xi + c_3\xi^2$, whose coefficients are computed as per Section 3.4, the nearest point to \mathbf{x}_m^k on $P_2(\xi)$ can be determined by minimising the function describing the squared distance between \mathbf{x}_m^k and $P_2(\xi)$. This results in the following cubic function whose roots are to be computed,

$$4c_3^2\xi^3 + 6c_3c_2\xi^2 + 2(c_2^2 + 2c_3(c_1 - x_{m,\eta}^k) + 1)\xi + 2(c_2(c_1 - x_{m,\eta}^k) - x_{m,\xi}^k) = 0$$

where $x_{m,\xi}^k$ and $x_{m,\eta}^k$ are the ξ - and η -components of \mathbf{x}_m^k , respectively. This is solved analytical using the well-known Cardano's formula for cubic equations. Since the above function could result in at most three roots, the nearest point is computed by determining the root corresponding to the minimum distance from \mathbf{x}_m^k to $P_2(\xi)$ (denoted as \mathbf{x}_{near} in Fig. 11). Since the vector from \mathbf{x}_m^k to \mathbf{x}_{near} must necessarily be orthogonal to $P_2(\xi)$, the normal \mathbf{n}_m^{k+1} can be computed as

$$\mathbf{n}_m^{k+1} = \text{sgn}(\mathbf{n}_m^k \cdot \mathbf{v}_{near}) \frac{\mathbf{v}_{near}}{|\mathbf{v}_{near}|} \quad \text{where} \quad \mathbf{v}_{near} = \mathbf{x}_{near} - \mathbf{x}_m^k \quad (16)$$

The following section concludes the iterative interface normal refinement procedure.

3.5.3. Iterative Procedure

Algorithm 3 details the normal refinement procedure for all columns. The procedure terminates when the residuals of the components of each interface normal fall below a prescribed residual tolerance R_{tol} . However in practice, the results in Section 4.2 demonstrate that at most 4 iterations are required to maximise the accuracy of interface curvature available to the scheme.

Algorithm 3 Iterative interface normal refinement procedure.

Input: Interface normal residual tolerance \mathcal{R}_{tol} .

Output: Compute the interface normals associated with the interface vertices of all columns in Z .

```

1: procedure COMPUTEINTERFACENORMALS( $\mathcal{R}_{tol}$ )
2:   set  $\mathcal{R}_x, \mathcal{R}_y \leftarrow \mathcal{R}_{tol} + 1$  //  $x$ - and  $y$ -residuals for the interface normals.
3:   set  $k \leftarrow 0$  Iteration counter.
4:   while  $\mathcal{R}_x > \mathcal{R}_{tol}$  or  $\mathcal{R}_y > \mathcal{R}_{tol}$  do
5:     set  $Z \leftarrow$  Array of columns intersecting the interface.
6:     for all interface vertices  $i$  do
7:       set  $\mathbf{n}_i \leftarrow$  Compute nodal normal for current iteration.
8:       add  $Z \leftarrow$  CONSTRUCTCOLUMNS( $i, \mathbf{n}_i, \theta_B, \alpha_{tol}$ )
9:     end
10:    for all  $\zeta_m \in Z$  do // Interface reconstruction.
11:      Construct PLIC facet in  $\zeta_m$  as per Section 3.2.
12:    end
13:    set  $\mathcal{R}_x, \mathcal{R}_y \leftarrow 0$  // Zero residuals.
14:    for all  $\zeta_m \in Z$  do // Compute the interface normal for each column  $\zeta_m$  in  $Z$  for iteration ( $k + 1$ ).
15:      set  $Z_m, stenType \leftarrow$  COMPUTECOLUMNSTENCIL( $\zeta_m$ )
16:      set  $\mathbf{n}_m^k \leftarrow$  Interface normal associated to  $\zeta_m$  in the current iteration.
17:      if  $stenType = 0$  then // Symmetric stencil.
18:        set  $\mathbf{n}_m^{k+1} \leftarrow$  Compute interface normal using Eq. (15).
19:      else // Asymmetric stencil.
20:        set  $\mathbf{n}_m^{k+1} \leftarrow$  Compute interface normal using Eq. (16).
21:      end
22:      set  $\mathcal{R}_x \leftarrow \mathcal{R}_x + (n_{m,x}^{k+1} - n_{m,x}^k)^2$ 
23:      set  $\mathcal{R}_y \leftarrow \mathcal{R}_y + (n_{m,y}^{k+1} - n_{m,y}^k)^2$ 
24:    end
25:    set  $\mathcal{R}_x \leftarrow \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{R}_x}{size(Z)}}$ 
26:    set  $\mathcal{R}_y \leftarrow \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{R}_y}{size(Z)}}$ 
27:    set  $k \leftarrow k + 1$ 
28:  end

```

Figure 12: PLIC facets describing a portion of a circular interface (a) before, and (b) after the iterative procedure.

The reader is here reminded that it is necessary to update the normals of all interface vertices at the end of each iteration (see line 7 in Algorithm 3), as it is the normals at the interface vertices that inform the direction in which

columns are to be constructed in the next iteration. Following the interface reconstruction, the PLIC facet normals are subsequently updated at lines 18 and 20 in Algorithm 3.

For all interface vertices at which only one column is constructed, the normal at the vertex is interpreted as the normal of the PLIC facet constructed in its column. For all vertices at which two columns are constructed, the normal at the vertex is taken to be the mean of the normals of the PLIC facets in the respective columns. The next section details the curvature computation procedure once the iterative normal computation procedure is converged.

3.6. Computing Curvature from the Interface Reconstruction

Unlike the procedure for computing the interface normal, the interface curvature is only computed for symmetric stencils. This is because, using an approach similar to that illustrated in Fig. 11 to compute curvature, results in large variations in the curvature accuracy between asymmetric and adjacent symmetric stencils. Therefore, since asymmetric stencils only occur at the ends of an overlapping region of PLIC facets, they can be omitted for the curvature computation as long as sufficient overlap is ensured.

The curvature at the interface vertex of the central column in a symmetric stencil is interpreted as the analytical curvature of the polynomial computed at the centroid of the central PLIC facet. For an n^{th} -order polynomial $P_n(\xi) = c_1 + c_2\xi + \dots + c_{n+1}\xi^n$, whose coefficients are computed in the manner detailed in Section 3.4, this corresponds to computing the curvature of $P_n(\xi)$ at $\xi=0$, which can be expressed as

$$\kappa = \frac{2c_3}{(1 + c_2^2)^{3/2}} \quad (17)$$

Following the computation of curvature for all symmetric stencils, it is necessary to apply the curvature values to the mesh vertices in each column to form a curvature ‘band’ over the interface. This is to ensure that the effects of the $\nabla\alpha$ and $(\nabla\alpha/\rho)_f$ terms respectively, in Eqs. (23) and (30), are fully accounted for over a potentially smeared VOF interface. For columns that do not lie in the overlapping region, each vertex in the column inherits the curvature associated to the column. For columns in the overlapping region, weighting factors are computed for each column, and the curvature is interpolated from the overlapping layers. This is to be done in a manner that bounds the error in the interpolated curvature to be between the errors from each layer. To this end, the weighting factors are computed based on the interface normals in the overlapping region, as the iterative refinement procedure results in a considerably smooth distribution of the normals (see Fig. 12).

Figure 13: Calculation of curvature weighting factors for two columns ζ_0 and ζ_1 , that are connected to an interface vertex i .

The procedure for computing the weighting factors is illustrated in Fig. 13. Firstly, all interface vertices in the overlapping region are visited and the weights for the two connected columns (ζ_0 and ζ_1 in the figure) are computed. With reference to the figure, the weights for ζ_0 and ζ_1 respectively, are $r_{\zeta_0} = \theta_1 / (\theta_0 + \theta_1)$ and $r_{\zeta_1} = \theta_0 / (\theta_0 + \theta_1)$. Finally, all mesh vertices in each column in the overlapping region are visited. If a vertex j is connected to two columns ζ_p and ζ_q , which both lie in the overlapping region, the weighted curvature at j is computed as

$$\kappa_j = \frac{\kappa_p r_{\zeta_q} + \kappa_q r_{\zeta_p}}{r_{\zeta_p} + r_{\zeta_q}} \quad (18)$$

where κ_p and κ_q respectively, are the curvature values computed in columns ζ_p and ζ_q . It must be noted that Eq. 18 interpolates curvature most accurately for the interface nodes in the overlapping region. The curvature at nodes that are farther away from the interface is less accurately interpolated, because the centroids of the PLIC facets (at which curvature is computed) associated to columns connected to such nodes are farther apart. However, this is not an issue because the curvature contribution of nodes that are away from the interface is hugely diminished by the magnitude of the $\nabla\alpha$ and $(\nabla\alpha/\rho)_f$ terms in Eqs. (23) and (30).

4. Results and Discussion

A set of three meshes of varying fineness was used to evaluate the accuracy and performance characteristics of the developed interface curvature calculation. Two interface types were considered – a circular interface of radius $0.25m$ and an elliptical interface whose major and minor axis lengths are $0.5m$ and $0.4m$, respectively. The volume fraction field for each interface type was initialised using the algorithm proposed by Jones *et al.* [28], which allows for initialisation of the VOF field to machine-precision accuracy. The interface was positioned at four different locations in each mesh as shown in Fig. 14 (centred at $x \in \{0.0, 0.067, 0.133, 0.2\}$). The positions were chosen so as to ensure that two of them would result in overlapping columns for both interface types – this occurs when $x=0.133$ and $x=0.2$.

Figure 14: The four positions of the circular interface with centers marked on the x -axis, shown on the second coarsest mesh.

Tables 1 and 2 list, for each case, the total number of mesh vertices whose control volumes are intersected by the interface, and the characteristic PLIC facet length, $L_2(\Delta)$. The latter characteristic is the L_2 -norm of the lengths of the PLIC facets representing the interface. For some attribute ψ , the following definition of the L_2 -norm, which is equivalent to the root-mean-square (RMS), is used

$$L_2(\psi) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_p} \sum_p (\psi_p)^2} \quad (19)$$

where N_p is the number of PLIC facets and ψ_p is the value of the attribute associated to PLIC facet p . Another metric that is utilised in the following sections is the L_∞ -norm, which is defined as

$$L_\infty(\psi) = \max\{\psi_p\} \quad (20)$$

The reader is here reminded that the curvature need only be computed at symmetric stencils. Therefore, Eqs. (19) and (20) only apply to all PLIC facets p that are in symmetric stencils. Further, Sections 4.1 and 4.2 solely analyse the accuracy implications for curvature computed at symmetric stencils.

Table 1: Mesh information for the circular interface. N_i refers to the number of vertices whose control volumes are intersected by the interface and $L_2(\Delta l_p)$ is the L_2 -norm of the lengths of the PLIC facets.

Mesh #	No. of Vertices	$x = 0.0$		$x = 0.067$		$x = 0.133$		$x = 0.2$	
		N_i	$L_2(\Delta l)$	N_i	$L_2(\Delta l)$	N_i	$L_2(\Delta l)$	N_i	$L_2(\Delta l)$
1	561	40	3.93e-2	40	4.00e-2	38	4.31e-2	36	4.70e-2
2	1121	56	2.81e-2	56	2.86e-2	52	3.02e-2	50	3.32e-2
3	2361	80	1.96e-2	80	2.00e-2	76	2.16e-2	74	2.30e-2

Table 2: Mesh information for the elliptical interface.

Mesh #	No. of Vertices	$x = 0.0$		$x = 0.067$		$x = 0.133$		$x = 0.2$	
		N_i	$L_2(\Delta l)$	N_i	$L_2(\Delta l)$	N_i	$L_2(\Delta l)$	N_i	$L_2(\Delta l)$
1	561	40	3.61e-2	40	3.69e-2	34	4.42e-2	32	4.58e-2
2	1121	56	2.58e-2	56	2.64e-2	48	3.16e-2	46	3.27e-2
3	2361	80	1.81e-2	80	1.85e-2	70	2.16e-2	68	2.22e-2

4.1. Curvature Grid Convergence Study

4.1.1. Circular Interface

The interface curvature κ_p is computed at all PLIC facets p at interface positions $x=0.0$ and $x=0.2$, and compared to the analytical curvature of the circle $\kappa_{circ} = -4.0 m^{-1}$ (an outward-pointing interface normal is assumed, resulting in negative curvature). Of all the cases, these two positions were considered to be the best and worst cases for the circular interface, respectively. Figs. 15 and 16 show the curvature relative error distributions around the interface. The horizontal axes of the figures is the angle that is subtended by the x -axis and line joining the centre of the circular interface and the point on the polynomial fit, at which the curvature was computed for each PLIC facet. In the local reference frame of a polynomial $P_n(\xi)$, this is the point $(0, P_n(0))$, as per Eq. (17). Given a computed numerical curvature κ_{num} , the relative error is computed as $\epsilon_{rel} = (\kappa_{num} - \kappa_{circ})/\kappa_{circ}$.

Figure 15: Curvature relative error distribution with second-order (P_2) and fourth-order (P_4) polynomial fits on mesh 1 for the circular interface centred at $x=0.0$.

The above is a case where there are no overlaps in the columns. This results in a smooth variation of the curvature relative error. Figs. 16(a) and 16(b) show the relative error plots at $x=0.2$ with the curvature computed using second-order polynomial fits for the coarsest and finest meshes, respectively.

Figure 16: Curvature relative error distribution for (a) mesh 1, and (b) mesh 3, for the circular interface centred at $x=0.2$. The red dotted line is the relative error of the proposed curvature interpolation procedure (see Section 3.6).

Fig. 16 depicts a case where there are overlapping regions of columns. The resulting discrepancy in the magnitude of the relative error is seen in the overlapping regions of the black dotted curves in the plots. This discrepancy will naturally be greater for larger degrees of anisotropy of the mesh near the overlapping regions. The red dotted line represents the relative error of the interpolated curvature value computed as per Eq. (18). This demonstrates that a smooth transition of the curvature in the overlapping regions is achieved via the developed scheme.

Figure 17: Grid convergence plots of (a) $L_2(\epsilon_{rel})$, and (b) $L_\infty(\epsilon_{rel})$, for the circular interface.

Fig. 17 depicts the computed curvature grid convergence characteristics of $L_2(\epsilon_{rel})$ and $L_\infty(\epsilon_{rel})$ for the circular interface at all four interface positions. The plots clearly demonstrate formal second- and fourth-order accuracy of the scheme for both $L_2(\epsilon_{rel})$ and $L_\infty(\epsilon_{rel})$.

4.1.2. Elliptical Interface

An elliptical interface was selected to evaluate the performance of the curvature calculation on interfaces with varying curvature. Referring to Fig. 18, and assuming an outward-pointing interface normal, the analytical curvature of an ellipse can be computed via a projection onto a circle as

$$\kappa_{\text{elli}}(\theta) = \frac{-r_x r_y}{(r_x^2 \sin^2 \theta + r_y^2 \cos^2 \theta)^{3/2}}$$

where r_x and r_y are the major and minor radii of the ellipse and θ is the angle corresponding to some point \mathbf{x} on the ellipse, as illustrated in Fig. 18. For the chosen elliptical interface, $r_x = 0.25$ and $r_y = 0.2$.

Figure 18: Calculation of the angle corresponding to point \mathbf{x} on an elliptical interface with major and minor radii r_x and r_y , respectively.

For all PLIC facets that do not lie in the overlapping region, the point \mathbf{x} is taken to be the point on the polynomial curve at which curvature was computed for the given PLIC facet. The procedure for PLIC facets in the non-overlapping region will be outlined shortly. Given a computed numerical curvature κ_{num} , at the point \mathbf{x} on the ellipse, the relative error in curvature is expressed as $\epsilon_{\text{rel}} = (\kappa_{\text{num}} - \kappa_{\text{elli}}(\theta)) / \kappa_{\text{elli}}(\theta)$.

Figure 19: Curvature relative error distribution with second-order (P_2) and fourth-order (P_4) polynomial fits on mesh 1 for the elliptical interface centred at $x=0.0$.

Fig. 19 shows the relative error plots for the elliptical interface at $x=0.0$ for the coarsest mesh. The above plots demonstrate that, for cases with no overlapping columns, the relative error in curvature varies smoothly for an elliptical interface, and thereby any interface with smoothly varying curvature.

Fig. 20 depicts a case with overlapping columns, where the elliptical interface is positioned at $x=0.2$. The figure illustrates the manner in which the curvature computation scheme interpolates the curvature in the overlapping region. Here, the curvature is computed using second-order polynomial fits.

Figure 20: Curvature relative error distribution for (a) mesh 1, and (b) mesh 3, for the elliptical interface centred at $x = 0.2$. The curvature is computed using second-order polynomial fits.

The analytical curvature in the overlapping region is computed by interpolating that associated to the two overlapping PLIC facets, using the same weights as those applied to the corresponding numerical curvatures via Eq. (18). The associated angle of each interpolation point is taken to be the angle θ that matches $\kappa_{elli}(\theta)$ with the aforementioned interpolated analytical curvature. Fig. 20 shows that Eq. (18) successfully bounds the error in the interpolated curvature between the errors of the overlapping layers.

Fig. 21 shows the grid convergence characteristics of $L_2(\epsilon_{rel})$ and $L_\infty(\epsilon_{rel})$ for the elliptical interface at all four interface positions. This case also clearly demonstrates the scheme’s ability to compute curvature to formal second- and fourth-order accuracy.

Figure 21: Grid convergence plots of (a) $L_2(\epsilon_{rel})$, and (b) $L_\infty(\epsilon_{rel})$, for the elliptical interface.

4.2. Curvature–Interface Normal Sensitivity Study

Since the iterative procedure for the interface normals was adopted as a means of maximising the accuracy of interface curvature, it is instructive to investigate the change in accuracy of the computed curvature after each iteration.

Figs. 22 and 23 show the convergence plots of the L_∞ -norm of the curvature relative error for all cases at positions $x = 0.0$ and $x = 0.2$. This is done by computing the curvature using second-order polynomial fits after each iteration.

Figure 22: Convergence history of the L_∞ -norm of the relative error in curvature during the iterative normal refinement procedure for the circular interface at (a) $x=0.0$, and (b) $x=0.2$.

Figure 23: Convergence history of the L_∞ -norm of the relative error in curvature during the iterative normal refinement procedure for the elliptical interface at (a) $x=0.0$, and (b) $x=0.2$.

The plots demonstrate that, based on the worst case positions for the circular and elliptical interfaces (Figs. 22(b) and 23(b)), the iterative procedure requires at most 4 iterations until the accuracy of the curvature computation is maximised. Note that the same study performed with fourth-order polynomial fits yielded the same result.

4.3. Stationary Bubble

This section investigates the scheme's ability to minimise the generation of spurious currents [1, 2] over time. This is done by simulating a stationary bubble [29]. At the equilibrium condition, the following should hold,

$$-\nabla p + \sigma\kappa\nabla\alpha = 0$$

However, discretisation errors typically introduce spurious velocities. The Laplace number, $La = \sigma\rho D/\mu^2$, is the ratio of surface tension to fluid momentum, where $D = 0.5m$ is the diameter of the bubble. Fig. 24 depicts the evolution of the non-dimensionalised RMS velocity over time on Mesh 1 (see Table 1) for $La = 1.2e4$ and a liquid-gas density ratio of 1000. In addition, to investigate the effect of the interface crossing multiple co-centric rows of vertices (see Fig. 1), the mesh is 'compressed' by reducing all y -coordinates by 20%. This is represented by the blue line.

Figure 24: Evolution of the RMS velocity for a circular droplet in equilibrium for the compressed and uncompressed mesh 1 with curvature computed using second-order and fourth-order polynomial fits.

Time is normalised with respect to the viscous time scale as per [12],

$$T_\mu = \frac{\rho D^2}{\mu}$$

And the RMS velocity is normalised with respect to the time scale

$$U_\sigma = \frac{\sigma}{\rho D}$$

The results demonstrate that, for both second- and fourth-order curvature computation, the scheme adequately damps spurious velocities down to similar levels as previous work using the HF method on Cartesian meshes [2, 12].

In addition to investigating the velocity evolution, it is instructive to demonstrate that the second-order convergence of curvature reflects in the Laplace pressure jump, $\Delta p = \sigma\kappa$, across the interface. To this end, the L_2 -norm of the pressure jump, $L_2(\Delta p)$, over each column was computed. Figs. 25 and 26 shows the evolution of $L_2(\Delta p)$, which converges relatively quickly in comparison to the RMS velocity.

Figure 25: Evolution of the L_2 -norm of the relative error in the Laplace pressure jump for a circular bubble in equilibrium, with curvature computed using second- and fourth-order polynomial fits, on the uncompressed version of mesh 1.

Figure 26: Evolution of the L_2 -norm of the relative error in the Laplace pressure jump for a circular bubble in equilibrium, with curvature computed using second- and fourth-order polynomial fits, on the compressed version of mesh 1.

The converged values of the pressure jump were used to perform a convergence study using all meshes. Fig. 27 confirms that the scheme achieves formal second- and fourth-order accuracy for the pressure calculation as well.

Figure 27: Laplace pressure jump convergence study with curvature computed using second-order (P_2) and fourth-order (P_4) polynomial fits.

4.4. Oscillating Droplet/Column in Zero Gravity

Another standard test case for evaluating the accuracy of the surface tension scheme is that of an oscillating droplet in an inviscid fluid in zero gravity [3, 35–38]. Consider a 2D droplet whose initial perturbed interface is given by

$$r = r_0 + \epsilon \cos(n\theta),$$

where n is the mode of oscillation and ϵ is a small-amplitude perturbation about a mean radius r_0 . The analytical oscillation frequency [39, 40] for the above interface is

$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{n(n^2 - 1)\sigma}{(\rho_0 + \rho_1)r_0^3}}, \quad (21)$$

where ρ_1 and ρ_0 are the fluid densities inside and outside the droplet, respectively. The above solution holds when the droplet is surrounded by a fluid of infinite mass [39]. The test case in this article was set up similar to that in Torres and Brackbill [35] and Hermann [37], except with a density ratio of 1000, as used by Fuster *et al.* [38]. An interface with $r_0 = 2m$, $\epsilon = 0.001m$, $\rho_0 = 0.001 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $\rho_1 = 1 \text{ kg/m}^3$, and $\sigma = 1 \text{ N/m}$, was centred at $(0, 0)$ in a circular domain of radius $2.0e4m$ with slip boundary conditions. The relatively large radius of the outer boundary was chosen because Eq. (21) holds for a droplet surrounded by a fluid of infinite mass [39]. A new set of four curvilinear meshes was generated in order to match the circumferential and radial mesh spacing with that used by the compared works [35, 37, 38]. A time-step size of $\Delta t = 1.0e-4s$ is used for all four meshes. Fig. 28 shows the comparison of the accuracy in computed frequency for $n = 2$.

Figure 28: Comparison of the accuracy in computed frequency for a droplet/column oscillating with mode $n=2$.

The results demonstrate that second-order accuracy is achieved for both the second- and fourth-order curvature computation schemes. The inability to achieve fourth-order accuracy is attributed to the second-order accurate discretisation of the other terms in the governing equations.

4.5. Computational Cost

To assess the computational cost, the proposed scheme was time-profiled over 1000 time-steps of the stationary bubble simulation from the previous section, which was run on a workstation with a 3.5GHz AMD Ryzen Threadripper 2920X 12-core processor.

Table 3: Time comparison of various components of the interface reconstruction procedure in a single column.

Component	% of Total Time
Convex decomposition	45.03
Vertex sorting	25.69
PLIC facet computation	11.65
Bracketing	8.47

Table 3 presents the time comparison of components that comprise the interface reconstruction procedure for a single column at a single iteration of the interface normal refinement procedure. It is clear that the convex decomposition (CD) is the most costly component of the algorithm. It is precisely this cost that López *et al.* [34] sought to avoid through the development of a procedure for general non-convex polygons and polyhedrons without the need for CD.

However, it is worth noting that since a vertex-centred approach is employed in this work, storage costs are reduced by not explicitly storing the geometry of median dual-cells. Instead, each dual-cell is computed *ad hoc*. Therefore, the cost of CD is dominated by traversing the local connectivity of a mesh vertex, and cumulatively constructing the faces of its dual-cell. Since this would be required regardless of whether a CD approach is employed, the work of López *et al.* is not expected to significantly offset this cost. Ofcourse, if the dual-cell geometries are stored, the scheme outlined in [34] would be almost twice as fast as the proposed interface reconstruction procedure. However, this would significantly increase the storage costs. An alternative approach, to be investigated in future work, is the decomposition of only a portion of the column that lies in the vicinity of where the PLIC facet is expected to be.

Table 4 shows the time comparison between the curvature computation and the incompressible flow solver for an average time-step. The results shown are specifically for the circular interface on meshes 1 – 3, with curvature computed using second-order polynomial fits.

Table 4: Time comparison of curvature computation scheme and the incompressible solution procedure in a single time-step.

Component	% of Total Time		
	Mesh 1	Mesh 2	Mesh 3
Incompressible solver	30.55	49.92	69.40
Curvature computation	69.45	50.08	30.60

It is worth noting that the additional cost introduced to the scheme when using fourth-order polynomial fits for curvature computation is insignificant. This is because the PLIC reconstruction procedure currently dominates the cost of the curvature computation scheme.

5. Conclusion

This paper presents a novel method for the accurate second- and fourth-order computation of interface curvature on curvilinear meshes for the purpose of surface tension modelling. The scheme obtains a conservatively constructed PLIC representation of the interface, and employs local polynomial fits through the PLIC facets for the curvature computation. The normals of the PLIC facets are refined iteratively, which is shown to maximise the curvature accuracy available to the scheme. Further, the scheme is shown to result in a considerably smooth distribution of curvature over the interface. The proposed method is rigorously tested for a variety of analytical interface types, whose positions are varied on a set of curvilinear meshes. The curvature scheme is implemented into a balanced-force continuum-surface-force surface tension model for variable-density flows. Both the curvature and the Laplace pressure jump across the interface are shown to be formally second- and fourth-order accurate. A significant reduction in the magnitudes of spurious velocities was achieved when simulating a stationary bubble with a density ratio of 1000, and a stable result was achieved for **both the second- and fourth-order curvature schemes. Similarly, the frequency of an inviscid oscillating droplet in zero gravity was computed to second-order accuracy for both curvature schemes, owing to the second-order discretisation of the remaining terms in the governing equations.**

Acknowledgements

This work is based on the research supported in part by the National Research Foundation of South Africa [grant number 89916]. The opinions, findings and conclusions or recommendations expressed is that of the authors alone, and the NRF accepts no liability whatsoever in this regard. This research was also supported by Ariane Group (AG). The authors would like to thank Dr. Philipp Behruzi (AG) and Mr. Francesco De Rose (AG) for their key insights that contributed to the development of this research.

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Appendices

A. Temporal Discretisation

Firstly, the volume fraction field is updated from

$$\alpha^{n+1} = \alpha^n - \frac{\Delta t}{\mathcal{V}_i} \sum_{f \in \partial\Omega_i} \alpha_f \mathbf{u}_f \cdot \mathbf{n}_f A_f$$

where $\partial\Omega_i$ is the set of faces that constitute the boundary of a median dual-cell Ω_i , \mathcal{V}_i is the volume of Ω_i , \mathbf{n}_f is the outward-pointing face normal, and A_f is the face area. Further, α_f is the volume fraction at a face which is evaluated using CICSAM [45], and \mathbf{u}_f is the face velocity which utilises the divergence-free velocity on the left-hand side of Eq. (22) shown below. The standard semi-implicit fractional step methodology [25, 26] is used to discretise the temporal term in Eq. (1) as

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\mathbf{u})}{\partial t} \approx \frac{\rho\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \rho\mathbf{u}^n}{\Delta t} = \frac{\rho\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \rho\mathbf{u}^*}{\Delta t} + \frac{\rho\mathbf{u}^* - \rho\mathbf{u}^n}{\Delta t}$$

from which the projected velocity field \mathbf{u}^* is solved explicitly by equating

$$\frac{\rho\mathbf{u}^* - \rho\mathbf{u}^n}{\Delta t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u})^n + \nabla \cdot (\mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T))^n$$

Next, the pressure field is solved implicitly from the Pressure Poisson equation

$$0 = \nabla \cdot \left[\mathbf{u}^* - \frac{\Delta t}{\rho^{n+1}} (\nabla p - \sigma\kappa\nabla\alpha)^{n+1} \right] \quad (22)$$

Lastly, the velocity field is updated by equating

$$\frac{\rho\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \rho\mathbf{u}^*}{\Delta t} = (-\nabla p + \sigma\kappa\nabla\alpha)^{n+1} \quad (23)$$

In this work, the surface tension term is added into Eqs. (22) and (23) in order to ensure a well-balanced scheme.

B. Balanced-force Surface Tension Spatial Discretisation

A vertex-centred, edge-based finite volume method is employed for spatial discretisation purposes. The pressure term in Eq. (22) is discretised at a vertex i as

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p \right) \approx \frac{1}{\mathcal{V}_i} \sum_{f \in \partial\Omega_i} \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p \right)_f \cdot \mathbf{n}_f A_f = \frac{1}{\mathcal{V}_i} \sum_{f \in \partial\Omega_i} \left(\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p \right)_f^{\parallel} + \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p \right)_f^{\perp} \right) \cdot \mathbf{n}_f A_f, \quad (24)$$

where $(\nabla p/\rho)_f^{\parallel}$ and $(\nabla p/\rho)_f^{\perp}$ respectively, are the components of $(\nabla p/\rho)_f$ that are parallel and perpendicular to the edge attached to face f . By defining the unit edge tangent of an edge connecting nodes i and j as $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{ij} = \mathbf{t}_{ij}/\|\mathbf{t}_{ij}\|$, where $\mathbf{t}_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i$, the perpendicular component is computed as

$$\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p \right)_f^{\perp} = \mathbf{v}_f - (\mathbf{v}_f \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{ij}) \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{ij}, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{v}_f = \frac{\nabla p_i + \nabla p_j}{\rho_i + \rho_j}. \quad (25)$$

Here, the computation of the nodal pressure gradients ∇p_i and ∇p_j is outlined shortly, in Eqs. (28) and (29). Next, to compute the $(\nabla p/\rho)_f^{\parallel}$ component, a compact stencil method [43] is employed. To this end, based on an approach similar to that of Panahi *et al.* [42], the following is assumed:

$$\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p \right)_f^{\parallel} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{ij}} = c_p,$$

where $\partial p / \partial \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{ij}$ is the directional derivative of p in the direction of $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{ij}$ and c_p is constant over the edge. By integrating the above along the edge from vertex i to the face f , and assuming a piecewise-constant density distribution in each dual-cell, the change in pressure between the vertex and the face can be expressed as

$$p_f - p_i = \frac{\|\mathbf{t}_{ij}\|}{2} \rho_i c_p \quad (26)$$

Likewise, integrating from f to j results in

$$p_j - p_f = \frac{\|\mathbf{t}_{ij}\|}{2} \rho_j c_p \quad (27)$$

The constant c_p is obtained by adding Eqs. (26) and (27) to get

$$c_p = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{ij}} = \frac{2(p_j - p_i)}{\|\mathbf{t}_{ij}\|(\rho_i + \rho_j)}$$

Lastly, the pressure at face f is obtained by subtracting Eq. (27) from Eq. (26),

$$p_f = \frac{\rho_j p_i + \rho_i p_j}{\rho_i + \rho_j}, \quad (28)$$

which is used to compute all nodal pressure gradients ∇p_i , used in Eqs. (23) and (25), by applying Gauss-Green's Theorem,

$$\nabla p_i \approx \frac{1}{\mathcal{V}_i} \sum_{f \in \partial \Omega_i} p_f \mathbf{n}_f A_f \quad (29)$$

In order to create a well-balanced scheme, the surface tension term in Eq. (23) is discretised in a manner that is consistent with the discretisation of the pressure gradient term in Eq. (24),

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma \kappa}{\rho} \nabla \alpha \right) \approx \frac{\sigma}{\mathcal{V}_i} \sum_{f \in \partial \Omega_i} \kappa_f \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla \alpha \right)_f \cdot \mathbf{n}_f A_f \quad (30)$$

where $\kappa_f = (\kappa_i + \kappa_j)/2$ is the curvature at face f , and the $(\nabla \alpha / \rho)_f$ term is discretised in exactly the same manner in which the $(\nabla p / \rho)_f$ term was discretised previously, except with all p terms replaced with α . As with the nodal pressure gradient, $\nabla \alpha_i$ is evaluated using α_f as computed by the equation equivalent to Eq. (28).